

Facile synthesis and antimicrobial screening of some biorelevant thiosemicarbazone and its analogues

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Abstract : Few new thiosemicarbazones (**2** and **3**) have been synthesized by condensing 2-hydroxy-5-(substituted phenyl azo) benzaldehyde **1(i)** and *p*-substituted phenyl thiosemicarbazide **1(ii)** in DMSO to enhance its medicinal value. The compounds are reported along with their spectral data, antifungal and antibacterial activities.

Keywords : Antimicrobial activity, thiosemicarbazones, thiosemicarbazone analogues.

Thiosemicarbazones with their complexing behaviour and biological activities are new clinical candidates in view of new substitutes for resistance against advanced generation drugs¹. The derivatives of this "nucleus compound" is a promising compound against various microbes and assessed with various therapeutic efficacy². Prompted by the aforesaid pharmaceutical activities³, we aimed at developing new approaches for the synthesis of substituted thiosemicarbazones and its derivatives in order to study their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Results and discussion

A series of thiosemicarbazones namely 2-hydroxy-5-(substituted phenyl) thiosemicarbazones (**2** and **3**) were obtained by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-(substituted phenyl azo)benzaldehyde **1(i)** and *p*-substituted phenyl thiosemicarbazide **1(ii)** in DMSO according to Scheme 1. All the products obtained are crystalline solids having sharp melting points, soluble in dimethyl formamide and have been characterized by elemental and spectral studies.

Antimicrobial screening : All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against two bacterial pathogens namely *S. aureus* and *S. typhimurium* at 1000 µg/disc and against two fungal pathogens viz. *C. neoformans* and *P. italicum* at 800 µg/disc by using disc diffusion assay⁴. For this, sterile filter paper disks (6 mm) impregnated with fixed doses of compounds was placed on pre-inoculated surface. The disc bearing plates were incubated within 30 min at 37 °C for 24 h. After incubation, the inhibition zone diameters were measured. Chloramphenicol and Fluconazole were used as standard drugs for bacterial and fungal pathogens respectively. All the

Scheme 1

observations are given in Table 1. The results of antimicrobial screening reveal that incorporation of halogen moiety enhances the antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

All the commercial reagents used were of A.R. grade. They were distilled, purified and dried according to standard procedure. The thin layer chromatography was used to access the reactions and purity of the synthesized compounds. The

Note

Table 1. Antimicrobial screening data of compounds 2a-e and 3a-e^a

Compd.	Antifungal (at 800 µg/disc)		Antibacterial (at 1000 µg/disc)	
	<i>C. neoformans</i>	<i>P. italicum</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. typhimurium</i>
2a	6	7	8	14
2b	8	11	15	19
2c	8	9	16	21
2d	6	10	15	20
2e	9	10	8	28
3a	8	11	11	14
3b	13	14	28	29
3c	11	13	32	36
3d	14	16	28	22
3e	13	12	20	23
Fluconazole	26	24	–	–
Chloramphenicol	–	–	52	44

^aControl DMF no activity (diameter of zone of inhibition in mm).

melting points were determined on an electrical melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The elemental analysis were performed on Carlo-Erba 1108 whereas IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 Infracord spectrometer and ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Varian EM-390 Hz spectrometer. The starting compounds 2-hydroxy-5-(substituted phenyl azo)benzaldehydes 1(i) and *p*-substituted phenyl thiosemicarbazides 1(ii) were prepared according to the reported methods⁵.

2-Hydroxy-5-(phenyl azo)benzaldehyde-*N*⁴-(4'-methyl phenyl)thiosemicarbazone 2(e) : In a round flask, were taken a solution of *p*-methyl phenyl thiosemicarbazide (0.001 *M* in DMSO) to which were slowly added a solution of 2-hydroxy-5-(phenyl azo)benzaldehyde (0.001 *M* in DMSO) with continuous shaking. The product 2(e) was separated as light brown solid on addition of requisite amount of water, which was repeatedly washed with water followed by ethanol and is soluble in DMF and DMSO. Yield, 70%, m.p. 218 °C (Found : C, 63.92; H, 4.82; N, 17.01. C₂₁H₁₉N₅OS Calcd. for : C, 64.76; H, 4.91; N, 17.98%); IR (KBr) ν(cm⁻¹) : 3445–3240 (OH and NH), 2950 and 2860 (C–H, sp³), 3010 (=C–H, sp²), 1665 (C=N), 1600 (N=N), 1255 (C=S); ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.49 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.5 (1H, s, OH), 6.95–7.56 (12H, m, Ar-H), 10.32 (1H, s, =N–NH), 9.84 (1H, s, CH=N), 8.97 (1H, s, NH-Ar).

Similarly, other compounds : 2(a) m.p. 199°, 2(b) 193°, 2(c) 175°, 2(d) 198°, yield 60–70% were prepared.

2-Hydroxy-5-(fluoro phenyl azo)benzaldehyde-*N*⁴-(4'-methyl phenyl)thiosemicarbazone 3(e) : It has been prepared by the method adopted for the preparation of 2(e). Yield, 65%, m.p. 151 °C, C₂₁H₁₈N₅OFS Found : C, 63.35; H, 4.17; N, 17.65.; IR (KBr) ν(cm⁻¹) : 3445–3260 (OH and NH), 2995 (=C–H), 2850 and 2930 (C–H, sp³), 1660 (C=N), 1595 (N=N), 1255 (C=S), 1050 (C–F); ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.53 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.5 (1H, s, CH=N), 8.3 (1H, s, NH-Ar), 6.95–7.6 (11H, m, Ar).

Similarly other compounds : 3a m.p. 167°, (b) 142°, (c) 151°, (d) 145°, yield 60–70% were prepared.

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